

Diversity, Equity & Inclusion in Medical Education

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Citation: Makenzie Dye, Rebekah Lantz. Diversity, Equity & Inclusion in Medical Education. *Int Clin Med Case Rep Jour.* 2023;2(10):1-6.

Received Date: 5 April, 2023; **Accepted Date:** 7 April, 2023; **Published Date:** 10 April, 2023

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ABSTRACT

Diversity in medicine is a topic of growing interest in the healthcare industry. It has become increasingly clear that there exist significant disparities for historically underrepresented groups across different specialties in the US. Research has shown that these under representations and disparities have significant implications for patient care, including health outcomes of diverse communities. In this editorial, we highlight the current state of diversity within medical specialties, implications of these results, and areas for future improvement.

Keywords: Diversity; Equity; Healthcare industry

EDITORIAL

INTRODUCTION

The purpose of studying diversity in medicine is to better understand the current state of representation for underrepresented groups, and to identify the ramifications of this lack of diversity for patient care and health outcomes in the United States (US). Our analysis addresses underrepresented groups as well as highlights, identifies, and addresses barriers that may prevent diversity from being achieved in particular specialties. Ultimately, we can identify potential solutions and targeted strategies to increase representation within these fields.

GENDER

Females compose slightly more than half of the US population and this is reflected in the current application rates to medical school^[1-3]. However it should be noted that females are more poorly represented with progressive advancement in career. Where 47% of resident and fellow trainees are women, 37% of the active practicing physician workforce, 38% of medical school faculty members, 21% are full professors, 18% are hospital CEOs, and 16% are dean and department chairs^[4-6]. Despite significant progress in gender equality and female representation, women remain underrepresented in many surgical and non-surgical specialties. In 2018,

the American Association of Medical Colleagues (AAMC) reported that for female residents, gender disparity was most common in surgical training^[3]. The five specialties with the lowest percentage of female residents at the time included pain medicine (26%, N=319), thoracic surgery (21%, N=244), interventional radiology (20%, N=215), neurosurgery (18%, N=1479), and orthopedic surgery (15%, N=4410)^[4]. More recently the lowest percentile specialties are radiology (26.6%), urology (23.7%), thoracic surgery (22.5%), neurosurgery (16.7%), and orthopedics (13.8%)^[3].

Orthopedic surgery remains historically and consistently the most male-dominated specialty with the least promising advances in female representation^[7-8]. In 2005-2006, females composed 3% but only increased to 14% in the decade to the 2016-2017 matriculation year. Compared to neurosurgery which increased 56.8% and thoracic surgery which increased 111.2% in the same period of time, female representation in orthopedics only increased by 11%^[7]. There should be improvement for gender representation across fields, but this is especially true for orthopedics.

RACE AND ETHNICITY

Minority representation in medical specialties remains a notable issue in the US. Despite efforts to diversify the physician workforce, minorities continue to be underrepresented, leading to disparities in patient care and outcomes^[9-10].

Nguemni et al categorized representation by a specialty representation quotient (SRQ), which determined the level of over or underrepresentation of students belonging to a particular racial or ethnic group, where an $SRQ > 1$ signified an overrepresented group within a given specialty and an $SRQ < 1$ signified an underrepresented group. The specialties with the greatest representation for racial and ethnic groups were family medicine ($SRQ=1.70$), physical medicine and rehabilitation ($SRQ=1.60$), and obstetrics/gynecology ($SRQ=1.47$). The specialties with the lowest representation were orthopedic surgery ($SRQ=0.86$), otolaryngology ($SRQ=0.53$), and plastic surgery ($SRQ=0.47$)^[11].

It was interesting to note that orthopedics again showed slower comparative advances for underrepresented groups. Among physicians practicing in the field in 2018, whereas 84.7% of physicians identify as Caucasian, 6.7% identify as Asian, 2.2% as Hispanic, 1.9% as Black and 0.4% as Native American^[8]. More diversity is needed for race and ethnicity representation.

IMG

Patients who are non-US origin have recognized difficulties navigating the healthcare system and culture within the US related to reasons of mannerisms, faith, and normalcies. While Bazargan et al present regarding race that even perceptions about trustworthiness of the medical field matter to patient health^[10], this is true for other

matters of identity for a patient including their country and region of origin. The concept of shared decision making that Dobler et al discuss is easier for the patient and provider alike when they already have similar background^[12].

Currently about a quarter of the total graduate medical education (GME) training pool and active physician workforce consist of international medical graduates (IMGs)^[13]. IMGs are more likely to enter primary care specialties than non-IMG peers, and IMGs disproportionately fill particular specialties. For example, 24% or more active practicing physicians are GME-trained IMG and form the backbone of internal medicine, psychiatry, neurology, and pathology. IMGs are least likely to be represented in orthopedic surgery (6%), dermatology (5%), radiation oncology (2%), and otolaryngology (1%)^[13].

Patients present to every specialty and may have more difficulty understanding explanations related to particular organ systems, beyond primary care matters. For example conservative females may have reservations about male provider exams, however physician availability may already be limited. Referring providers should discuss these matters with patients, in observation of their background and preferences in foresight to prevent uncomfortable situations for patients. However it would be encouraged that IMG be represented even for specialties beyond those where they are most prominent, currently in primary care but less represented in elsewhere.

DISCUSSION

As the population becomes more diverse, it is important to have a physician workforce that reflects this diversity. Currently there is a falling short of this principle.

Failure to adequately reflect the gender diversity of the patient population may negatively impact patient outcomes. Studies show practice pattern differences between male and female physicians, where female practitioners may more likely adhere to clinical guidelines and evidence-based practice as perceived rule followers^[14]. Also, female providers provide preventive care more frequently, utilize patient-centered communication better per patient satisfaction scores, and provide more psychosocial counseling^[14-16].

Improving access to quality healthcare and reducing health disparities for minority patients can be achieved by increasing the number of racial and ethnic minority physicians. Underrepresented groups in medicine disproportionately serve minority patients more, and patients prefer physicians of similar racial and ethnic backgrounds^[17-18]. For example, Ku et al showed that Black, Latino, and Asian patients were more likely to display patient-physician concordance than expected by three-times, strongly preferring clinicians of the same race or ethnicity and had a positive reflected on patient scores regarding the patient-physician interaction^[18].

IMGs tend to practice in primary care, underserved areas, and rural locations, addressing an important healthcare shortage[13]. Meanwhile patient outcomes are equivalent or better for persons treated by IMGs, with providers fulfilling IMG training with lower mortality rates compared to US medical trained graduates and US citizens attaining their degrees abroad^[19].

In order to improve the health outcomes of an increasingly diverse patient population, it is important to improve diversity among trainees and physicians who ultimately practice in leading roles. To achieve this goal entails attracting, recruiting, and retaining physicians who have been historically underrepresented in medicine^[20]. This may start with outreach programs to garner awareness at an early career level with science, technology, engineering and mathematics (STEM) programs to attract high school students to the healthcare career and in medical school to recruit DO/MD candidates toward diverse residency programs^[21-22]. It may entail improving wellness programs and making work-life balance achievable for females and alternate healthcare providers who hold traditional household roles as well as their goals in career advancement^[23-26]. It will start with improving opportunities and going against bias to choose a diverse presenter that are shown as equally competent in field such as publishing, presenting, and leading from early career stages onward^[27]. Underlying the mentioned ambitious initiatives, it is imperative to reduce discriminations and aggressions toward minorities and to overall improve representation toward a new normal that looks more richly cultural and diverse^[28-30]. Overall, increasing diversity from the early years of interest in the healthcare field through training and into practice will be meaningful to improve access to quality healthcare in underserved areas, reduce health disparities, and promote high quality patient-centered outcomes.

CONCLUSION

Diversity representation is important for patient outcomes and for the landscape of medicine. We discuss the most commonly recognized disparities of gender, race, and IMG but diversity is not limited to these. Initiatives look like starting outreach at early stages of career pursuits, increasing wellness and awareness into training and practice, providing opportunities for research and leadership, and recognizing and reducing the acceptance of micro aggressive behaviors toward minority groups. When the situation improves internally to the medical field, patient satisfaction and health data are likely to follow as shown.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST AND DISCLOSURE STATEMENT

The author has declared that no financial support was received from any organization for the submitted work. The author has declared that there are no financial relationships at present or within the previous three years with any organizations that might have an interest in the submitted work. The author has declared that there are no other relationships or activities that could appear to have influenced the submitted work.

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